

THE ROLE OF MOTIVATION AND SELF-MANAGEMENT IN ONLINE LANGUAGE LEARNING

Isamova Fariza Zafarovna

a master's student of the Foreign Language and Literature department of the Samarkand branch of the ISFT Institute, student of group 25-SXTAM-02.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20617648>

Annotation. *The role and importance of motivation and self-management in the process of online language learning is analyzed. The issues of effective organization of students' educational activities, maintaining learning motivation and developing independent learning skills in modern digital education are covered. According to the results of the study, high motivation and developed self-management skills significantly increase the effectiveness of online language learning. The article also scientifically substantiates the importance of internal and external motivation, time management, goal setting and self-control in language learning.*

Keywords: *online learning, language learning, motivation, self-management, independent learning, digital technologies, learning autonomy, academic success, foreign language, self-control.*

РОЛЬ МОТИВАЦИИ И САМОУПРАВЛЕНИЯ В ОНЛАЙН-ИЗУЧЕНИИ ЯЗЫКОВ

Аннотация. *Анализируется роль и значение мотивации и самоуправления в процессе онлайн-изучения языков. Рассматриваются вопросы эффективной организации учебной деятельности студентов, поддержания учебной мотивации и развития навыков самостоятельного обучения в современном цифровом образовании. По результатам исследования, высокая мотивация и развитые навыки самоуправления значительно повышают эффективность онлайн-изучения языков. В статье также научно обосновывается важность внутренней и внешней мотивации, тайм-менеджмента, целеполагания и самоконтроля в изучении языков.*

Ключевые слова: *онлайн-обучение, изучение языков, мотивация, самоуправление, самостоятельное обучение, цифровые технологии, учебная автономия, академическая успеваемость, иностранный язык, самоконтроль.*

ONLAYN TIL O'RGANISHDA MOTIVATSIYA VA O'ZINI BOSHQARISHNING ROLI

Annotatsiya. *Onlayn til o'rganish jarayonida motivatsiya va o'zini boshqarishning o'rni hamda ahamiyati tahlil qilinadi. Zamonaviy raqamli ta'lim sharoitida o'quvchilarning o'quv faoliyatini samarali tashkil etish, o'quv motivatsiyasini saqlab qolish va mustaqil ta'lim ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish masalalari yoritilgan. Tadqiqot natijalariga ko'ra, yuqori motivatsiya va rivojlangan o'zini boshqarish ko'nikmalari onlayn til o'rganish samaradorligini sezilarli darajada oshiradi. Shuningdek, maqolada ichki va tashqi motivatsiya, vaqtni boshqarish, maqsad qo'yish hamda o'z-o'zini nazorat qilishning til o'rganishdagi ahamiyati ilmiy jihatdan asoslangan.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** onlayn ta'lim, til o'rganish, motivatsiya, o'zini boshqarish, mustaqil ta'lim, raqamli texnologiyalar, o'quv avtonomiyasi, akademik muvaffaqiyat, chet tili, o'z-o'zini nazorat qilish.*

Introduction

The rapid development of information and communication technologies has brought new opportunities to the education system. In particular, the popularity of online learning platforms has made the process of learning foreign languages more convenient and popular. Today, millions of people are learning foreign languages remotely through Duolingo, Coursera, Udemy, Busuu, Memrise and other platforms. Online language learning differs from traditional classroom training in a number of ways. It requires the student to independently organize his activities, control the learning process and systematically work to achieve the goals he has set. Therefore, motivation and self-management skills are one of the most important factors in the success of online education.

Motivation represents an individual's internal or external incentive to perform a certain activity. In language learning, motivation encourages the student to acquire new knowledge, overcome difficulties and continue his educational activities. Self-management refers to a person's ability to plan, control and evaluate their own activities. Especially in online education, these skills are one of the main conditions for successful learning. Nowadays, thanks to the development of the Internet and modern technologies, learning foreign languages has become much easier. If earlier it was necessary to attend courses or educational institutions to learn a language, today there is an opportunity to learn a language anywhere and at any time through online platforms.

The convenience, flexibility and availability of many resources of online education are the reasons for its popularity. However, success in online education does not depend only on technology. The motivation and self-management of the student play an important role in this process. Learning a language is a long process that requires constant work and patience.

Especially in online education, the student works more independently. Therefore, motivation and self-management skills are an integral part of the learning process. Motivation is an internal or external factor that encourages a person to move towards a certain goal. In language learning, motivation is important for a student to continue learning, acquire new knowledge, and overcome difficulties. There are 2 types of motivation, which are: Internal motivation and external motivation. Internal motivation is formed based on a person's own interests and needs. For example, someone learns English to understand foreign films without translation, while another learns a language to travel the world or make friends from different countries. Such motivation is strong and long-term. External motivation, on the other hand, arises under the influence of external factors and includes; getting a good job, entering higher education, obtaining an international certificate, increasing salary, and the demands of parents or teachers. Often, internal and external motivation work together in language learning.

Motivation and self-control are complementary concepts. Motivation encourages a person to take action, while self-control directs this action in the right direction.

For example, if a student sets a goal to obtain an international certificate, this is his motivation. To achieve this goal, doing daily exercises, planning his time and monitoring his results is a process of self-control. If there is motivation but no self-control, it will be difficult to achieve the goal. On the contrary, if self-control is good but motivation is not enough, the student may lose interest in continuing to study.

Therefore, both should develop together.

The importance of motivation in online language learning: Motivation is the driving force of the language learning process. Students with high motivation regularly attend classes, do more exercises, do not give up quickly on difficulties, and actively absorb new knowledge. Studies show that students with a high level of motivation achieve significant results in mastering a foreign language.

Time Management and Self-Directed Learning: While flexibility is a major advantage of online learning, it can also be a challenge for some students. If students do not plan their time properly, they may end up procrastinating or not completing their studies at all. Effective time management involves creating a daily plan, setting learning goals, prioritizing tasks, and setting up regular review sessions.

The Relationship Between Motivation and Self-Directed Learning: Motivation and self-directed learning are closely related. Motivation drives students to engage in activities, while self-directed learning enables students to help to organize effectively. For example, the desire to learn a foreign language perfectly (motivation) encourages the student to practice regularly, while time planning and control of results (self-management) ensure the achievement of the goal.

In conclusion, motivation and self-management are important pedagogical and psychological factors in the process of online language learning. If motivation is the main force that attracts the student to educational activities, then self-management serves to effectively organize this activity. Analyses show that students with high motivation and developed self-management skills achieve high results in online learning.

Therefore, it is important to support students' motivation in the educational process, to form independent work and self-control skills in them. In the future, expanding methodological and psychological research aimed at increasing the effectiveness of online language learning remains one of the urgent scientific tasks.

References:

1. Gardner R.C. Motivation and Second Language Acquisition. New York, 2010.
2. Dornyei Z. Teaching and Researching Motivation. Pearson Education, 2001.
3. Zimmerman B.J. Self-Regulated Learning and Academic Achievement. Routledge, 2008.
4. Benson P. Teaching and Researching Autonomy in Language Learning. Routledge, 2011.
5. Little D. Learner Autonomy and Language Learning. Dublin, 1991.
6. Harmer J. The Practice of English Language Teaching. Pearson Education, 2015.
7. Richards J.C., Rodgers T.S. Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching. Cambridge University Press, 2014.